

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring data into the Digital Twin Ocean

D2.5 Call for data grants_M16

18/12/2024

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D2.5 – Call for data grants_M16

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties

Keywords

Biodiversity; data; marine; grants; FSTP; open call

Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Despite significant advancements in Europe to collect, harmonise, and make available data on marine biodiversity, a large portion of data remains unavailable or inaccessible. This type of data is referred to as "sleeping data". To activate these sleeping data, two calls for marine biodiversity (monitoring) data are organized within the context of the project DTO-BioFlow. This document details the second of these data calls, launched on the 17th December 2024. The primary goal of the call is to establish workflows and procedures that promote and facilitate the sharing of critical missing marine biodiversity data, and ultimately to facilitate sustained and long-term ingestion of previously inaccessible data into the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO) through publication in EMODnet Biology. Applications can be submitted until February 28th 2025, at 23:59 CET. The evaluation process is scheduled to occur in March 2025. Eligible proposals will be selected based on multiple criteria, including their relevance, potential impact, ability to sustain data flow and automate processes, uniqueness, and overall proposal quality. Within the impact criterium, it will be assessed how much the proposed project would contribute to filling important identified gaps (temporal, geographic, taxonomic) in the biodiversity data coverage. Selected applicants will receive a Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) grant of up to €60.000.

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1. Call for marine biodiversity (monitoring) data

Within Task 2.5 two FSTP calls for data holders are organised. The primary goal of the calls is to establish workflows and procedures that promote and facilitate the sharing of critical missing marine biodiversity data, and ultimately to facilitate sustained and long-term ingestion of previously inaccessible data into the European Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO) through publication in EMODnet Biology. Details about the launch of the first call are available in D2.4 – *Call for data grants_M2*. The second call for marine biodiversity (monitoring) data was launched on the 17th of December 2024.

The full text describing all the call details can be found under section 1.1. *Call text*. In close collaboration with WP6 (Trust-IT), this text was published on the DTO-BioFlow website, on the following pages: <https://dto-bioflow.eu/open-calls> and <https://dto-bioflow.eu/second-open-call-marine-biodiversity-data>. In addition, a webform was set up by Trust-IT to receive the applications: <https://dto-bioflow.eu/second-open-call-marine-biodiversity-monitoring-data>, containing the questions specified under *Annex 2.1*, in addition to a file upload where the filled-in application template is to be uploaded. The application template can be found under *Annex 2.2*. The call is open for applications until the 28th of February 2025 at 23:59 CET.

The call was announced through several social media platforms, website news sections and mailing lists and will continue to be advertised throughout the time the call is open for applications. Targeted communications will be sent to data holders of prioritised unavailable data sources identified in D2.9 – *Prioritised inventory of unavailable data sources*.

The evaluation process is scheduled to occur in March 2025. Eligible proposals will be selected based on multiple criteria, including their relevance, potential impact, ability to sustain data flow and automate processes, uniqueness, and overall proposal quality. A ‘missing data score’ will be calculated for each application, based on the preliminary skill matrix assessing missing data in EMODnet Biology created in the framework of Task 2.3 – *Assessing the impact of missing data*. This score will be taken into account in the evaluation process under the impact criterium. The selected projects will receive up to €60.000 of financial support and will run for 12 months, from the 1st of May 2025 until the 30th of April 2026. Selected beneficiaries will participate in a data training workshop, which will take place from the 3rd to the 5th of June 2025 in Paris.

1.1. Call text

DTO-BioFlow – Call for marine biodiversity (monitoring) data

Background

The ocean and its biodiversity are essential to life on this planet. Comprehensive data on biodiversity, and related human and environmental pressures are crucial to understand its current state and how this may change. Protecting and restoring biodiversity is one of three objectives of the Horizon Europe Mission to restore our oceans and waters by 2030, enabling the EU to reach its Green Deal and Biodiversity 2030 targets. Identified as one of the Mission "enablers", the EU will build on "a digital knowledge system" to include a Digital Twin of the Ocean (EU DTO) allowing simulation of 'what if' scenarios, advancing ocean knowledge, informing evidence-based policy and offering a range of societal applications.

The DTO-BioFlow project

To effectively replicate the ocean's ecology, the DTO requires sustained flows of data on biodiversity and associated pressures. While biodiversity data are being collected by myriad actors, using a wide variety of methods (including novel cost-effective monitoring technologies), not all these data become publicly available in a standardized format. DTO-BioFlow will activate these "sleeping" marine biodiversity data and enable the sustainable integration of data flows from various sources to EMODnet and into the [EDITO](#) infrastructure serving the EU DTO.

Combining sustained data flows, models and new algorithms, DTO-BioFlow will develop and integrate the biological component of the DTO, including new digital tools and services. Policy-relevant use cases, will demonstrate the benefit for marine ecosystems of continuous data streams flowing through EMODnet and usable by the EU DTO infrastructures and ultimate end-users. For more information on the DTO-BioFlow project, visit the [project's website](#). The project runs from September 2023 to February 2027.

Call for proposals

We are pleased to announce the launch of this second call for marine biodiversity data holders who can contribute to the DTO-BioFlow project, by establishing ingestion pipelines to the EU DTO and thereby increasing the flow of relevant biodiversity data. This Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) grant can provide support to do so, by funding resources as well as facilitating a data training workshop for the selected applicants.

Project activities

The selected beneficiaries commit to carry out the following activities:

- Participate in a **dedicated workshop** which will provide training on how to reformat and quality control data conform international standards (see further) and make these available to EMODnet Biology, held from **the 3rd of June to the 5th of June 2025 in Paris** (3 full days). In-person attendance of at least one representative per selected beneficiary is required. It will also be possible to attend the training workshop online, in case multiple people per beneficiary want to attend the workshop but cannot all attend in person.
- **Complete the [online training course provided by EMODnet Biology](#)** (required for at least one representative per selected beneficiary).
- Contribute to the flow of marine biodiversity data into the DTO, through **developing data flow pipelines to EMODnet Biology**. Setting up a data flow through intermediate data systems that already have or will in the near future have a direct data flow pipeline to EMODnet Biology (e.g. ICES, ETN) is also eligible.
- Optimize the data flow so that it is as much as possible automated and commit to continued data submission, **ensuring sustained data flows to the DTO**.
- **Ensure the data is formatted, standardized, and quality-controlled** conforming to the relevant international standards (as demonstrated in the workshop and the EMODnet Biology online training course) (e.g. using the [Darwin Core standard](#) for biodiversity data, [OBIS-ENV-DATA](#) as the preferred format, [World Register of Marine Species](#), [Marine Regions](#) and [BODC NERC Vocabulary Server \(NVS\)](#) to standardize taxonomic names, location names and parameter names respectively, [EMODnet Biology QC Check tool](#) to perform quality checks).
- Ensure that metadata and data will become available through EMODnet Biology. Data need to be **published on an [Integrated Publishing Toolkit \(IPT\)](#) instance** and **pass the EMODnet Biology Quality Control process**.
- Ensure the **data complies to Open Access**, preferably under a Creative Commons [CC-BY license](#). If applicants plan to use any other license, this needs to be detailed in their application.
- Provide short **intermediary reports** on their progress every four months, and a **final report** on the results at the end of the 12-month project.

Who can apply

Eligible beneficiaries for this call are **data holders** (international networks, citizen science networks, research institutes, universities, NGOs, etc.) **who can facilitate sustained and long-term ingestion to the EU DTO of previously inaccessible data. Beneficiaries or affiliated partners of the DTO-BioFlow project cannot receive funding through this call.**

Entities subject to [EU restrictive measures](#) under [Article 29 of the Treaty on the European Union \(TEU\)](#) and [Article 215 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU \(TFEU\)](#) are not eligible to participate as recipients of this FSTP. Applicants should have a good command of English, **must be eligible for participation in the EC Horizon Europe Framework Programme** (see [list of participating countries](#)) and **must ensure to follow the following obligations of the [Grant Agreement](#)**: Articles 12 (conflict of interest), 13 (confidentiality and security), 14 (ethics), 17.2 (visibility), 18 (specific rules for carrying out action), 19 (information) and 20 (recordkeeping). The DTO-BioFlow project coordinator will also ensure that the bodies mentioned in Article 25 (e.g. granting authority, OLAF, Court of Auditors (ECA), etc.) can exercise their rights also towards the recipients.

Applicants **need to have the rights and permissions to work with the data**, and bring these into the public domain under an open license. The applicants need to declare that **all samples/materials underlying the data were collected in compliance with national & international legislation**, and be able to show the necessary documents when requested.

Applying organisations should be able to provide the personnel to carry out the activities defined in the application. Subcontracting of organisations not involved in the application is not allowed.

Funding

The maximum amount of financial support for each application is 60.000 EUR.

Half of the funding (50%) will be granted at the start of the project, the other half (50%) will be granted at the end of the project, which corresponds to a successful realization of the proposed activities.

List of costs that qualify for financial support:

- **Personnel costs** to execute the following types of activities:
 - Development of pipelines for data processing, reformatting, standardisation, transfer and publication
 - Development of data access API's (Application Programming Interface)
 - Data quality control
 - Data documentation and management (in accordance with FAIR principles)
- **Travel costs** to attend the 3-day data training workshop in Paris. At least one person and at most two persons per selected beneficiary should attend the workshop in person.

Note that no other costs, for example costs incurred for sample collection/analysis, **qualify for financial support through these grants.**

Application eligibility

To be eligible to receive this grant, applications need to meet the following criteria:

- The data conform to the requirements of the project:
 - **data is not readily available in the public domain, or is not in a standardized format.** Updating existing datasets such as time series by enriching them with previously unavailable data (e.g. more recent data) is eligible.
 - **data is marine biodiversity data:** taxon occurrences, preferably linked to (a)biotic measurements retrieved at the same time and location. New biological data types from methods or sensors capable

of species detection are eligible provided that temporal, geographic and taxonomic information is derived from them.

- data are, for a substantial part, **collected in European marine waters**.
- data can be published under an **open license** (preferably CC-BY).
- The data are **helping the project to reach its overall goals**:
 - filling important identified gaps in the biodiversity data coverage (e.g. poorly covered taxonomic groups, data poor regions, new data types).
 - facilitating a sustained and long-term ingestion and established data flow.
 - mobilizing marine biodiversity (monitoring) data and data series.
- The applicant is **not a beneficiary nor an affiliated party** to the DTO-BioFlow grant agreement.
- **Good quality plan of action**.
- **Successful realisation** of proposed activities.

Application process

Call launch: December 17th 2024

Deadline for applications: February 28th 2025, 23:59 CET

Single stage submission

Applicants should submit their application through the Open Call webform on the DTO-BioFlow website, where the filled-in application template needs to be submitted. If you do not already have an account on the DTO-Bioflow website, you will need to create one first to access the Open Call webform. [Register here!](#)

Timeline

March 31st 2025: Evaluation completed & beneficiaries informed

From May 1st 2025 to April 30th 2026 (12 months): Project implementation

June 3rd-5th 2025: Mandatory attendance of the planned workshop

August 31st 2025: First interim report + online course completion deadline

December 31st 2025: Second interim report deadline

April 30th 2026: Final report, data available and project completion deadline

Assessment process

The assessment panel will rate all eligible proposals, taking into account the following criteria:

- **Relevance:** The proposal conforms to the requirements, goals and scope of the DTO-BioFlow project.
- **Impact:** What will be the estimated impact? Size/number, frequency, continuance, and range (temporal/geographic/taxonomic) of proposed dataset(s) will be considered, in combination with how much the proposed data contribute to filling gaps in the current biodiversity data landscape (gaps could be taxonomical, geographical, methodological, etc.).
 - The following [ICES ecoregions](#) have the most missing data in EMODnet Biology: Arctic Ocean, Faroes, Greenland Sea, Iceland Sea, Azores, Ionian Sea and the Central Mediterranean Sea, and the Aegean-Levantine Sea. Projects containing data from within these regions will thus receive a higher impact score.

- **Sustained data flow & automation:** the data flows set up within the project are designed to continue beyond the duration of the project. They should be/are as much as possible automated and the applicants are willing to commit to a long-term data flow, beyond the duration of their grant and the DTO-BioFlow project duration.
- **Uniqueness:** the proposal does not overlap with existing data pipelines and networks.
- **Excellence/proposal quality:** the proposed actions are realistic, feasible, well-defined and in balance with the requested financial support.

An initial ranking will be constructed based on this evaluation. Additional factors might impact the final list of third parties receiving funding, such as the amount of requested budget, similarity to a higher ranked proposal, ethical concerns and potential conflicts of interest.

Privacy

Personal data will be collected, processed and published in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679, also known as GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) as detailed in the [DTO-Bioflow privacy policy](#).

Contact

Contact opencalls@dto-bioflow.eu for any questions about this call.

2. Annexes

2.1. Application webform

Title of the proposed project

Give a title for the proposed project in max. 150 characters.

Applicant details

Contact details of the person representing the applicant

Name	
Function	
Organization	
Email	

Contact details of the official who authorized this application and who holds the responsibility to ensure the proper execution of the proposed project as detailed in this application

Name	
Function	
Organization	
Email	

Data overview

Geographic

Please indicate in which [ICES ecoregion\(s\)](#) the data that will be part of the proposed project is collected.

- Adriatic Sea
- Aegean-Levantine Sea
- Arctic Ocean
- Azores
- Baltic Sea
- Barents Sea
- Bay of Biscay and the Iberian Coast
- Black Sea
- Celtic Seas
- Faroes
- Greater North Sea
- Greenland Sea
- Iceland Sea
- Ionian Sea and the Central Mediterranean Sea
- Norwegian Sea
- Oceanic Northeast Atlantic
- Western Mediterranean Sea

Temporal

Please indicate in which timerange(s) the data that will be part of the proposed project is collected.

- 1800-1899
- 1900-1999
- 2000-2009
- 2010-2020
- 2021-present
- Present-future

Taxonomic

Please indicate which phylum/phyla are present in the data that will be part of the proposed project.

- Acanthocephala
- Acidobacteria
- Acritarcha
- Actinobacteria
- Amoebozoa
- Annelida
- Anthocerotophyta
- Apusozoa
- Aquificae
- Arthropoda
- Ascomycota
- Bacillariophyta
- Bacteroidetes
- Basidiomycota
- Bigyra
- Brachiopoda
- Bryophyta
- Bryozoa
- Caldiserica
- Cercozoa
- Chaetognatha
- Charophyta
- Chlamydiae
- Chlorobi
- Chloroflexi
- Chlorophyta
- Choanozoa
- Chordata
- Chromeridophyta
- Chytridiomycota
- Ciliophora
- Cnidaria
- Crenarchaeota
- Cryptophyta
- Ctenophora
- Cyanobacteria
- Cycliophora
- Deferribacteres
- Deinococcus-Thermus
- Dicyemida
- Echinodermata
- Elusimicrobia
- Entoprocta
- Euglenozoa
- Euryarchaeota
- Fibrobacteres
- Firmicutes
- Foraminifera
- Fusobacteria
- Gastrotricha
- Gemmatimonadetes
- Glaucophyta
- Glaucophyta
- Glomeromycota
- Gnathifera
- Gnathostomulida
- Haptophyta
- Heliozoa
- Hemichordata
- Hemimastigophora
- Heterokontophyta
- Kinorhyncha
- Korarchaeota
- Lentisphaerae
- Loricifera
- Loukozoa
- Marchantiophyta
- Metamonada
- Microsporidia
- Mollusca
- Myozoa
- Nanoarchaeota
- Nematoda
- Nematomorpha
- Nemertea
- Nitrospirae
- Ochrophyta
- Oomycota
- Orthonectida
- Percolozoa
- Phoronida
- Picozoa
- Placozoa
- Planctomycetes
- Planctomycetota
- Platyhelminthes
- Porifera
- Prasinodermatophyta
- Priapulida
- Proteobacteria
- Radiozoa
- Rhodelphidia
- Rhodophyta
- Rotifera
- Spirochaetes
- Spironematellophyta
- Sulcozoa
- Synergistetes
- Tardigrada
- Tenericutes
- Thaumarchaeota
- Thermodesulfobacteria
- Thermotogae
- Tracheophyta
- Verrucomicrobia
- Xenacoelomorpha
- Zygomycota

Application form

Upload the completed application form. The application form template can be downloaded [here](#).

2.2. Application template

Call for marine biodiversity (monitoring) data

Application form

General information

Title of the proposed project

Give a title for the proposed project in max. 150 characters.

Summary

Summarize the proposed project in max. 500 words.

Organization(s)

Give the name, type (e.g. NGO, scientific institution, government, etc.) and country of the organization(s)/institute(s)/entities involved in the implementation of the proposed project.

Current situation

Current data format & storage

Describe the current format of the data and where it is currently stored in max. 200 words.

Current challenges

Describe the current challenges for making these data openly available in max. 250 words.

Existing data flows and other right holders

Describe if and how the data are part of any existing data flows. Describe if there are other right holders to the data than the organization(s) involved in this application, and if they were contacted to check that there are no other existing or planned data flows. Max. 200 words.

Funding & data requirements

Describe which funding was used for the data collection and if it came with any requirements towards making the data available in max. 200 words.

Project details

Objectives of the proposed project

Describe the objectives of the proposed project in max. 500 words.

Methodology of the proposed project

Give a detailed description of the planned approach to accomplish the proposed project's objectives. Include how you plan to perform the data processing and how you will establish the data flow to EMODnet Biology. Max. 750 words.

Sustained data flow

Describe how the data flow is envisioned to continue beyond the end of the proposed project. Include a description of which funding is available / can be expected for future data collection. Include how sustained data flow to the DTO will be ensured after the end of this project. Max. 500 words.

Impact on existing data flows

Describe how the proposed project will impact existing data flows, if those exist, in max. 200 words.

Data details

Title(s) of the dataset(s) that will be part of the proposed project

Give the title(s) of the dataset(s) that will be part of the proposed project, together with their first contact person and – where possible – the citation of each dataset and where additional information on their metadata can be consulted (published report, web page, ...), in max. 200 words.

Current data description

Give a description of the currently existing data that will be published during the proposed project. Make sure to include under which framework the data were originally collected (e.g. national monitoring, research project, historic data), temporal cover, geographic cover, taxonomic cover, dataset size (number of records), methodologies used to collect the data, and which parameters (e.g. counts, biomass) are included. Max. 350 words.

Future data description

Give a description of the future data expected to flow to the DTO because of the pipelines set up in the proposed project. Make sure to include under which framework the data will be collected (e.g. national monitoring, research project, historic data), expected temporal cover, expected geographic cover, expected taxonomic cover,

estimated expected order of magnitude of the dataset(s) (number of records), methodologies that will be used to collect the data, and which parameters (e.g. counts, biomass) will be included. Max. 350 words.

License

Under which license will the data be made available?

- CC-BY Other

If you indicated "Other", specify which license and the reason for choosing this license instead of CC-BY in max. 150 words.

Relevance and impact

Describe the relevance and the impact of the proposed project in max. 250 words.

Budget

Indicate your planned budget (max. total €60.000). Note that the grant can only be used for personnel costs related to data documentation/standardisation/quality control and setting up data flow pipelines, and travel costs for 1 or 2 persons to attend the 3-day data training workshop in Paris.

Requested grant amount (€)	
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Briefly describe how the requested budget will be used in (e.g. "N Person Months for a [profile/function name (e.g. data manager, ITeR, researcher)] to perform the the following main tasks: ...", "travel costs for 1 person ([profile/function name]) to attend the workshop", etc.). Max. 250 words.

